

**CULTURAL CONCEPTS IN THE LIGHT OF CONCEPTUALIZATION
OF COGNITIVE METAPHORS**

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Abstract: This article aims to figure out cultural concepts in English and Uzbek literary works. It should be noted that the notion of “concept” is regarded as one of the core terms of Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology, Linguoconceptology, and other anthropocentric language sciences. According to cognitive linguistics, a “concept” is a complex mental unit, a way of representing knowledge structures, a multifold cognitive structure, and an operational memory unit. The novelty of this research is to identify cultural concepts in the works of “The Lion’s skin” by Somerset Maugham and “Hazrati Inson” by Rahmat Fayziy and analyze them according to the concept analysis process. The method that was used in the research work is comparative analysis.

Keywords: cognitive metaphor, cultural concept, notional, image-bearing and evaluative components of concept, conceptsphere, cognitive structure.

The notion of “concept” is regarded as one of the core terms of Cognitive Linguistics, Linguoculturology, Linguoconceptology, and other anthropocentric language sciences. Many definitions presented for “concept” in the works of foreign and Russian scientists, including M. Heidegger, G. Lakoff, G. Picht, G.V. Alefirenko, N.D. Arutyunova, S.A. Askoldov, A.P. Babushkin, G.I. Berestenev, E.S. Kubryakova, D.S. Likhachev, and others, who define both differences and some common characteristics of this notion. According to cognitive linguistics, a “concept” is a

complex mental unit, a way of representing knowledge structures, a multifold cognitive structure, and an operational memory unit.¹

Linguoculturologists define “concept” as “a basic unit of culture, its core; a mental, cultural, and nationally specific unit characterized by a range of emotional, expressive, and evaluative components; an essential element of the national conceptosphere”.²

Regardless of some differences in approaches, as V.I. Karasik indicates, “linguacultural and cognitive approaches to the notion of concept are not incompatible: concept as a mental unit in the mind of the individual provides access to the conceptosphere of society, whereas cultural concept is a unit of collective cultural experience; it becomes the cultural property of each person”.³ As a result, a concept is a complex mental entity, an aspect of the conceptual world picture that is conceptually significant to an individual linguistic personality or the entire linguocultural community.

Most scholars, including V.I. Karasik (2001, 2004), G. Slyshkin (2001), S.G. Vorkachyov (2004, 2007), and others, believe that “concept” is made up of three parts: 1) notional (factual information, the concept’s basic, essential, and distinguishing properties); 2) image-bearing (metaphors based on the principle of analogy); 3) evaluative (evaluation and behavioral norms, axiological, and cultural components).⁴

As it has been mentioned, cultural concept is the result of cultural experience and it provides cultural information about one nation. Cultural concepts can also reflect national characteristics in literary texts, folks, songs and poems. Furthermore, they serve as a verbalizer of conceptualization of cognitive metaphors. So, in this paragraph, we have decided to analyze cultural concepts which were represented in literary works.

¹ Демьянков В. З. Доминирующие лингвистические теории в конце XX века// Язык и наука конца 20 века: Сб. статей. – М., 1995. Кубрякова Е.С. Начальные этапы становления когнитивизма: лингвистика, психология, когнитивная наука//Вопросы языкознания. – 1994. – № 4. – С. 34-47. Алефиренко Н.Ф. Современные проблемы науки о языке. – М.: Наука, 2005. Болдырев Н. Н. Концепт и значение слова//Методологические проблемы когнитивной лингвистики. – М.: 2001. – С. 27-31

² Ashurova D. and Galiyeva M. Cognitive linguistics. Toshkent: “VneshInvestProm. 2018.

³ Карасик В. И. Языковой круг: личность, концепты, дискурс. – М.: Гнозис, 2004. – 390 с.

⁴ Ashurova D. and Galiyeva M. Cognitive linguistics. Toshkent: “VneshInvestProm. 2018.

The first work to analyze is “The Lion’s skin” by Somerset Maugham. First and foremost, the plot and details of the story are introduced in a short way.

“The Lion’s Skin” was written by William Somerset Maugham, a notable 19th century English writer. Mr. Forestier, the main character, has never been a true gentleman and does not hail from a wealthy family. He had spent his entire life as a servant in various gentlemen’s clubs, where he was treated admirably. And throughout his life he wished to be one of them, to be a true gentleman. Eleanor’s money gave him the opportunity to become who he wanted to be. So, after he married her, he began to “wear a lion’s skin,” claiming to be a nobleman on the outside while being a sheep on the inside. And it was a huge blow to him when Fred Hardy discovered his true descent and began mocking him.

The action takes place in a hospital in 1916. Eleanor met her future husband there. The story depicts the narrative of a man who has always wanted to be a gentleman. The war provided him with an opportunity. Eleanor’s money made it possible. The novel has various sad and tragic situations. Their villa caught fire one day when Forestier was not at home. It was too late to do anything, so Eleanor cried, “My little dog, it’s in the fire!” Mr. Forestier whirled around and dashed back to the house. He wanted to save the dog and show how a gentleman should act. To make a long tale short, they discovered him dead on the landing, clutching a dead dog.

Mr. Forestier lived to represent a real English gentlemen during his life. He was not born to be a gentlemen. However, his character and bravery make him gentlemen. He proved that being a real gentlemen does not mean that you have to be born as a gentlemen, but you should behave and act as a gentlemen. In the story, there are some fragments which illustrate Mr. Forestier as a gentlemen.

“The trouble was that Captain Forestier was **almost too perfect a type of the English gentleman**. He was at forty-five (he was two or three years younger than Eleanor) still a very handsome man, with his wavy, abundant grey hair and his handsome moustache; he had the weather-beaten, healthy, tanned skin of a man who is much in the open air. He was tall, lean and broad-shouldered. He looked every inch a

soldier. He had a bluff, hearty way with him and a loud, frank laugh. In his conversation, in his manner, in his dress he was so typical that you could hardly believe it.”⁵

According to this fragment, cultural concept “gentlemen” illustrates conceptual information about the role of “gentlemen” in English society. In the next stage, we will analyze the concept “gentlemen” with respect to the analysis of three constituents of the concept.

The notional part of the concept includes the bare minimum of its main properties, as defined by dictionary definitions. In other words, the notional constituent requires a comparison of meanings from various dictionaries.

Gentlemen – 1) a polite way of talking to or referring to a man; 2) a man who is polite and behaves well towards other people, especially women; 3) a man of a high social class; ⁶4) a man of noble or gentle birth; 5) a man belonging to the landed gentry; 6) a man who combines gentle with birth or rank with chivalrous qualities; 7) a man whose conduct conforms to a high standard of propriety or correct behavior; 8) a man of independent means who does not engage in any occupation or profession for gain; 9) a man who does not engage in a menial occupation or in manual labor for gain;⁷ 10) a man who treats other people in a proper and polite way; 11) used especially in polite speech or when speaking to a group of men.⁸

The image-bearing component is indicated by metaphorical linguistic expressions: idioms, word-formation units, proverbs, sayings, quotations, aphorisms and texts. Now, we will analyze each constituent individually.

Idioms: a gentleman and a scholar, a gentleman from the old school, gentleman of the four outs, gentleman’s agreement, gentleman’s pact, the little gentleman in the velvet coat.⁹

⁵ The Complete Short Stories (Volume I) of W. Somerset Maugham, from Project Gutenberg Canada

⁶ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/gentleman>

⁷ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/gentleman>

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/dictionary/gentleman>

⁹ <https://idioms.thefreedictionary.com/gentleman>

Word-formation units: gentlemanliness, gentlemanly, gentlemanlike, gentlemanlikeness.

Proverbs: 1) If everyone were a gentleman, who would make the mills work? (Russian Proverbs); 2) What is it to be a gentleman? Firstly, it is to be thankful and secondly to complain. (Serbian Proverbs); 3) Education begins a gentleman, conversation completes him. (English Proverbs) 4) Bargain like a gypsy, but pay like a gentleman. (Hungarian Proverbs)¹⁰

Sayings, quotations and aphorisms: The word of a gentleman is as good as his bond; and sometimes better (Charles Dickens); Better make penitents by gentleness than hypocrites by severity (Saint Francis de Sales); There are no gentlemen in anything competitive – you want to win (Len Goodman); The gentleman is a Christian product. (George Henry Calvert); A gentleman has ease without familiarity, is respectful without meanness; genteel without affectation, insinuating without seeming art (Philip Dormer Stanhope); Come, gentlemen, I hope we shall drink down all unkindness (William Shakespeare); He is the best gentleman that is the son of his own deserts, and not the degenerated heir of another's virtue (Victor Hugo); The flowering of civilization is the finished man, the man of sense, of grace, of accomplishment, of social power—the gentleman (Ralph Waldo Emerson); The look of a gentleman is little else than the reflection of the looks of the world (William Hazlitt).¹¹

The evaluative component analysis is concerned with uncovering people's attitudes toward a concept (good/bad), its axiological relevance, and is performed on all language methods conveying a concept. As an example, **GENTLEMEN IS A PERFECT ENGLISH MAN** can be categorized as cognitive metaphor. We can define this cognitive metaphor with such descriptions: In his conversation, in his manner, in his dress **he was so typical** that you could hardly believe it. He was **so much of a country gentleman** that he made you think rather of an actor giving a

¹⁰ Source: <https://proverbicals.com/gentleness-proverbs>

¹¹ <https://www.brainyquote.com/topics/gentleman-quotes>

marvellous performance of the part. When you saw him walking along the Croisette, **a pipe in his mouth, in plus-fours and just the sort of tweed coat he would have worn on the moors**, he looked so like an English sportsman that it gave you quite a shock. And his conversation, **the way he dogmatised, the platitudinous inanity of his statements**, his amiable, well-bred stupidity, were all **so characteristic of the retired officer** that you could hardly help thinking he was putting it on.¹²

According to the concept analysis of “gentlemen”, the denotative meanings and linguistic metaphorical expressions represent that the attitude towards “gentlemen” in English culture is positive. When it comes to this concept, people think about a perfect type of men: well-mannered, well-educated, handsome, polite and noble men. So, gentlemen is a type of men who can be an example of ideal men in English society. In “The Lion’s skin”, Captain Robert Forestier can be considered as gentlemen with his noble characteristics which stand out others.

The next novel to analyze cultural concept is “Hazrati Inson” by Rahmat Fayziy. The novel was written in 1969 and it depicts the life of the Uzbek people who took part in the Second World War from the back of battle field. The characters of the novel are ordinary and hardworking people. Especially, Mahkam aka and Mehrinisa opa have adopted fourteen children who were orphans and came to Uzbekistan from other foreign countries during the war. The main theme of the novel is to show how a real human being should behave in front of the difficulties, when it comes to help others and be generous. Mahkam aka and Mehrinisa opa are the examples of such kind of people. They are heroes who take care about others and share their kindness and love with orphan children. However, they do not have any children. This may be reason why they love strange children as their own. The title has also symbolic meaning. “Hazrati Inson” symbolizes the people who are kind, heartfelt, careful and ready to help others in any situation.

¹² The Complete Short Stories (Volume I) of W. Somerset Maugham, from Project Gutenberg Canada.

In this literary work, we analyze the concept “Hazrati Inson” according to the concept analysis guidelines. Firstly, denotative meanings of the concept are presented.

Hazrati Inson – 1) odamzod, bashar; 2) har bir yakka shaxs; 3) odam; 4) kimsaga (odatda, salbiy munosabatli) murojaat shakli. Xo‘, inson, bu nima noma’qulchilik, tilsiz jonivorda nima qasdingiz bor?! Mushtum¹³

The image-bearing component of the concept is represented by metaphorical linguistic expressions: idioms, word-formation units, proverbs, sayings, quotations, aphorisms and texts.

Proverbs: Baliq suvsiz yashamas, Inson – do’stsiz; Aql toshi – Inson boshi; Inson aqli bilan, dono naqli bilan; Inson aqli – olmos; Inson – odobi bilan, Osmon – oftobi bilan; Inson qo’li – gul; Gul – hayot bezagi, Sevgi – inson; Vatansiz inson — kuysiz bulbul; Ish — insonning gavhari; Suv o’jar, inson undan ham o’jar; Inson — gavhari Qobul; Anjom — uy ziynati, So‘z — inson ziynati; Inson bo’lsang vafo qil, Vafosizlik — xato, bil. Inson sevgi bilan tirik; Inson qalbi quyoshdan yorug; Inson qilolmaydigan ish yo’q. Insonning joni — toshdan qattiq, Ko‘ngli — guldun nozik; Inson umri — daryo suvi.¹⁴

Word-formation units: insoniylik, insoniy, insongarchilik, insoniyat, insoniylashtirmoq, insonlik, insonparvar, insonparvarlik, insonsevar, insonsevarlik, insonsifat, insontaxlit.¹⁵

The evaluative component analysis deals with revealing people’s attitudes toward a concept (good/bad), its axiological relevance, and is performed on all language methods conveying a concept. For example, the following cognitive metaphors can be created from the novel “Hazrati Inson”:

¹³ <https://savodxon.uz/izoh?inson>

¹⁴ Mirzayev T, Musoqulov A, Sarimsoqov B. “O‘zbek xalq maqollari”, “SHARQ” NASHRIYOT-MATBAA AKSIYADORLIK KOMPANIYASI BOSH TAHRIRIYATI TOSHKENT — 2005.

¹⁵ <https://savodxon.uz/izoh?inson>

1. **HAZRATI INSON – SODDADILLIK** (- Isitib deysizmi? Qiz boshi bilan-a? – Ha, voy. Issiq-sovuq deyapman – ku! **Soddasiz-a, aylanay, borib turgan soddasiz.** – Qayoqdan bilay, opa. Eshitaman-u nimaligini bilmayman.)¹⁶
2. **HAZRATI INSON – OLOV** (Mehrinisa o‘zicha **yonardi-yu**, eridan yashirardi.)¹⁷
3. **HAZRATI INSON – SABR-BARDOSH** (Har bir to‘y, kishilarning orzu-havaslari uning **qalbini tirnab o‘tardi-yu, sezdirmasdi.**)¹⁸
4. **HAZRATI INSON – YORUG‘LIK** (Qarang **nuroniychehراسi tongday yorishib**, kulib, qarab turibdi.)¹⁹

The concept analysis of “Hazrati Inson” indicates that denotative meanings are positive, there is no any negative attitude toward this concept. Moreover, proverbs about “Hazrati Inson” point out human being is the highest position in nature and he has a unique mind. Only human being can be patient in front of any difficulties and his heart is more delicate than flower. According to the analysis of cognitive metaphors, “Hazrati Inson” symbolizes naiveness, fire, patience and brightness.

In conclusion, cultural concepts have been analyzed using the concept analysis process. From English culture, the concept “Gentlemen” in the story “The Lion’s skin” has been studied and the cognitive metaphor GENTLEMEN IS A PERFECT ENGLISH MAN has formed. From Uzbek culture, the concept “Hazrati Inson” in the novel “Hazrati Inson” by Rahmat Fayziy has been studied and the cognitive metaphors HAZRATI INSON – SODDADILLIK, HAZRATI INSON – OLOV, HAZRATI INSON – SABR-BARDOSH, HAZRATI INSON – YORUG‘LIK have been made up.

¹⁶ Rahmat Fayziy “Hazrati Inson”, G’afur G’ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti, 1978, p- 18.

¹⁷ Rahmat Fayziy “Hazrati Inson”, G’afur G’ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti, 1978 p- 40.

¹⁸ Rahmat Fayziy “Hazrati Inson”, G’afur G’ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti, 1978, p- 40.

¹⁹ Rahmat Fayziy “Hazrati Inson”, G’afur G’ulom nomidagi adabiyot va san’at nashriyoti, 1978, p- 51.

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